

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN STEEL FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH UNIDIRECTIONAL AND QUASI-UNIDIRECTIONAL WOVEN ARCHITECTURES

Michaël Guy Callens¹, Larissa Gorbatikh¹ and Ignaas Verpoest¹

Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, 3001 Leuven, Belgium

Email: Larissa.Gorbatikh@mtm.kuleuven.be, web page: <http://composites-kuleuven.be>

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ABSTRACT

The effect of the microstructure on the tensile properties and failure behaviour of steel fiber composites is investigated. Two types of composites are produced: with quasi-unidirectional woven and perfectly unidirectional fibre architectures. The main difference in the two microstructures is the fibre distribution. In the quasi-UD composite, steel fibres are tightly packed in bundles with 85% of the local fibre volume fraction and these bundles are separated by resin rich areas. In the perfect-UD composite, steel fibers are homogeneously distributed throughout the composite with an average volume fraction of 50%. The quasi-UD composites with highly packed fibres are found to have a higher strain to failure. Acoustic emission registration was used to better understand the difference in fracture behaviour of these materials, affected by their microstructures.

1 INTRODUCTION

We have previously reported that ductile steel fibres deliver composites with a high strain-to-failure even in combination with a brittle epoxy matrix [1-4]. They exhibit a 3 to 5 times higher strain-to-failure than typical unidirectional carbon and glass fibre composites, and combine this with a high stiffness. The current research focuses on the importance of the microstructure of the steel fibre composites in determining their tensile properties. More specifically, the effect of the fibre distribution (variations in the local fibre volume fraction) on the mechanisms of failure development is of interest. This understanding is needed to further optimize properties of steel fibre composites and to fully exploit the potential of the ductile fibres. The fibre volume fraction was found to have an important effect on the mechanical behaviour of metal or ceramic matrix composites [5-7]. Depending on the fibre volume fraction different fracture modes could be activated and have a strong influence on both the strength and toughness of these composites. It is expected that the fibre volume fraction will also strongly influence the failure behaviour of steel fibre composites.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The fibres of a stainless steel alloy (316L) and with diameter of 30 μm are produced by NV Bekaert SA. The stress-strain curve of these fibres can be found in [9]. The fibres are supplied in the form of a quasi-unidirectional weave. The weft yarns are steel fibre yarns (275 fibres) and the warp yarns are untwisted thin polyester yarns; the latter have a volume fraction below 5%. The areal density of the fabric is 1425 g/m². This fibre architecture will be further referred to as Q-UD (“quasi” unidirectional). The second fibre architecture is obtained by manually removing the polyester yarn from the same Q-UD, resulting in a nonwoven UD material. This fibre architecture will be further referred to as P-UD (“pure” unidirectional). The matrix is an Epikote 828LVEL (a Bisphenol-A type) epoxy resin with a 1,2-diaminocyclohexane (Dytek DCH-99) as hardener (with the ratio 15.2 / 100).

Composite plates were produced using the vacuum assisted resin infusion technique. Three layers of the UD steel fibre fabrics were stacked to obtain UD laminates. Four layers were stacked for cross-ply laminates in (0,90)_s configuration, in order to realise a symmetric laminate. The resin was degassed for 15 minutes and impregnation was done at 40°C, curing at 70°C for 1h and post-curing at 150°C for 1h.

The tensile properties of these composites were tested according to ASTM D3039. The width of the samples was 15 mm for UD composites and 25 mm for cross-ply composites. The gauge length was 150 mm and no end tabs were used. The tests were performed on an Instron 4505 with a 100 kN load cell and under a rate of 2 mm/min. The strain was measured using an optical extensometer. The damage development was evaluated by acoustic emission (AE) registration using a VALLEN system and two V5375-M sensors. The fibre volume fraction is calculated based on the areal density of the fabric and the measured composite thickness.

3 MICROSTRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Figure 1 illustrates the difference between microstructures of the two UD composites. In Q-UD composites a high fibre volume fraction inside the steel yarns is observed, leading to a highly inhomogeneous microstructure. In P-UD composites, steel fibres can move laterally during compaction and hence are more homogeneously distributed through the thickness of the laminate.

Figure 1: (a) Images of two distinctly different microstructures for Q-UD (left) and P-UD composites (right); (b) relative distribution of the local fibre volume fraction in the two composites

In order to quantitatively characterise the microstructure, a Matlab program was written to determine the average global and local fibre volume fractions. According to the obtained histograms (Fig. 1b), in Q-UD composites about 30% of the volume is occupied by the resin rich zones and the volume fraction of steel fibres inside the yarns is around 85%. The P-UD composite has a more homogeneous

distribution of fibres with the histogram peak near 65%. The distribution in P-UD is also wider, from approximately 30% till 80%, while in Q-UD it is narrower and concentrated between 60% and 95%. The Q-UD has a lower overall fibre volume fraction due to the higher content of resin rich zones. The local fibre volume fractions can be used to estimate the average distance between fibres. It was concluded that a large number of fibres in Q-UD is about 4 times closer to each other than in P-UD. Moreover, in P-UD there are no fibres that are at distances 3 μ m or less away from each other.

3 TENSILE PROPERTIES

Results of the tensile tests on UD and cross-ply composites with both microstructures are shown in Table 1. All produced laminates show much higher strain-to-failure (up to about 15%) than typical glass and carbon fibre composites. This ductility is combined with a high stiffness. After normalization to the same fiber volume fraction, the only observed difference between the two materials is the strain-to-failure, which is about 35% higher in Q-UD composites both for cross-ply and UD composites.

Fabric	UD laminate		Cross-ply laminate	
	Q-UD	P-UD	Q-UD	P-UD
Fibre volume fraction	40.2 \pm 2.0%	49.8 \pm 1.2%	38.5 \pm 1.2%	53.0 \pm 2.1%
Sample thickness [mm]	1.33 \pm 0.07	1.04 \pm 0.02	1.93 \pm 0.03	1.32 \pm 0.04
Stiffness [GPa] - experimental	77.7 \pm 5.4	99.1 \pm 8.6	42.9 \pm 2.2	56.3 \pm 6.0
Yield stress [MPa] σ_{yield}	164.9 \pm 2.6	204.1 \pm 12.0	94 \pm 3.9	129.9 \pm 11.7
Strength [MPa] σ_{UTS}	269.5 \pm 5.6	313.5 \pm 30.6	123.5 \pm 7.6	168.2 \pm 17.7
Strain-to-failure, % ϵ_{ult}	15.4 \pm 1.4	11.4 \pm 3.6	14.8 \pm 2.4	10.7 \pm 2.7
Dissipated energy [J/mm ³]	36.7 \pm 3.7	34.9 \pm 10.8	16.9 \pm 3.2	17.6 \pm 5.4

Table 1: Tensile properties of the UD and cross-ply laminates

4 DAMAGE ANALYSIS

To better understand the difference in the failure strain, the damage development was analyzed. The specimen surface was photographed during the tensile tests to observe formation and development of cracks. At a strain of 5%, no damage could be seen on the surface of the P-UD composite, while in the Q-UD composite cracks were found near the transverse PET yarns. At higher strains (10%), even more cracks were found around the PET yarns and local debonding of the yarns could be seen in Q-UD composites. However, in P-UD composites still no cracks were visible. All Q-UD samples failed in a correct fashion, namely away from the clamps, while failure of P-UD samples was always initiated in the clamps. This incorrect failure could explain the lower strain-to-failure of UD laminates with the P-UD microstructure.

In cross-ply composites, at 5% of strain, transverse cracks are found in both composites, but their appearance is very different. In Q-UD composite, the transverse cracks grow to the surface by going around the 0 $^{\circ}$ steel yarns. In P-UD horizontal lines appear on the surface of the sample, indicating transverse cracks in the 90 $^{\circ}$ plies, but these cracks do not grow through the 0 $^{\circ}$ layers to the surface. At 10% strain, more transverse cracks are visible in Q-UD composite, which are accompanied by the debonding growth along the 0 $^{\circ}$ yarns. The distance at which these transverse cracks appear is consistent with the 90 $^{\circ}$ - steel fibre yarn spacing. Transverse cracks are likely to form in the middle of a 90 $^{\circ}$ - yarn where the highest stress concentrations are expected due to the tight fibre packing. Also in the P-UD more transverse cracks appear but still they do not grow through the 0 $^{\circ}$ layers to the surface. Final failure of the cross-ply composites occurs at failure of the longitudinal yarns.

Figure 2 a and b show a close-up of the sample in a region close to the final failure. In case of the Q-UD, the transverse cracks which have grown around the 0 $^{\circ}$ yarns to the surface are clearly visible. As mentioned before, the transverse cracks in the cross-ply of the P-UD have not grown to the surface and are hence not visible. Final failure occurs due to failure of the 0 $^{\circ}$ steel fibres. In case of the Q-UD,

the fibres do not seem to fail individually, but rather the entire yarn fails. Before final failure, a lot of crack bridging and pull-out of the entire yarn occurs. This appears to be less present in the P-UD. This could be the reason for the lower strain-to-failure found in the P-UD composites, both for the UD and cross-ply laminates, since crack bridging and pull-out can effectively delay the final failure.

Figure 2 c and d show a close-up of the side of a tested specimen showing a clear difference in the amount of delaminations. In case of the P-UD, the entire 90° ply is delaminated. This is seen for all samples close to the location of the final failure. Very limited delaminations are seen in case of the Q-UD. A hypothesis is that because the 0° remains more or less intact (i.e. the transverse cracks have not grown through this layer), local stress differences are larger between the cracked 90° layer and the 0° layer, which then promote delamination. This is in contrast with the Q-UD where the cracks grow around the 0° yarns and hence the 90° cracked layer is connected to the 0° yarns only locally.

Figure 2: Close-up on the failure location of the (a) weft Q-UD and (b) nonwoven UD. Side view of the failed cross-ply samples, (c) Q-UD and (d) P-UD.

The analysis of the surface cracks was also compared with AE results to understand how the damage develops internally. Much more events and of higher energy are recorded in Q-UD than in P-UD composite (Figure 3). This is in agreement with the crack observations: multiple cracks were found in Q-UD initiated at the PET yarn, while no cracks were visible to the naked eye in P-UD. The events that are measured in P-UD could be due to sub millimetre or sub micrometre cracks inside the composite. From 5% strain onwards, fewer events, but with higher energies, are measured in Q-UD. These are attributed to the cracks which grow around the 0° steel yarns. Because no transverse yarns are present in P-UD composite, the AE activity is very limited and also goes down after 5%.

In the case of cross-ply laminates more events and of higher energy are recorded than in the case of the UD laminates. The onset of the higher energy events in the cross-ply laminates started at $\pm 0.5\%$ strain. Higher energies were measured for the cross-ply laminates in which the Q-UDs were present. From 5% strain onwards, fewer events and of lower energies were recorded. Since the debonding of the 0° yarns is mainly seen in Q-UD and delaminations in P-UD, it is likely that the yarn debonding requires more energy than the growth of delaminations.

Figure 3: (a) Measured cumulative acoustic energy for each UD sample and (insert) average cumulative acoustic energy (b) Measured cumulative number of events for each UD sample and (insert) average cumulative number of events

9 CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research show that steel fibre composites combine both a high stiffness (approaching 100 GPa at $V_f = 50\%$) and strain-to-failure (up to 15%). The microstructure and more specifically the fibre distribution can alter the fracture behaviour of these composites. While a higher local fibre volume fraction increases local stress concentrations in the 90° layers and likely decreases the strength of these layers, the high fibre packing in bundles is shown to be beneficial for the increase of the failure strain of the 0° layers.

By analysing the damage development on the specimen surface and the AE data, a distinct difference was noted between the failure of the 0° layers with highly packed fibre bundles separated by resin rich zones and the layers with a more homogenous fibre distribution. It was suggested that the close packing of fibres forces cracks to grow around them rather than penetrate inside the bundles and start debonding of individual fibres. This delays necking of the fibres – a final stage of the composite failure. Additionally the close proximity of other steel fibres changes the stress state when a fibre starts necking. Thus, the presence of tightly packed bundles is found to increase the composite failure strain.

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